

Using *Cupriavidus necator* H16 to Provide a Roadmap for Increasing Electroporation Efficiency in Nonmodel Bacteria

Matteo Vajente, Riccardo Clerici, Hendrik Ballerstedt, Lars M. Blank, and Sandy Schmidt*

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ABSTRACT: Bacteria are a treasure trove of metabolic reactions, but most industrial biotechnology applications rely on a limited set of established host organisms. In contrast, adopting nonmodel bacteria for the production of various chemicals of interest is often hampered by their limited genetic amenability coupled with their low transformation efficiency. In this study, we propose a series of steps that can be taken to increase electroporation efficiency in nonmodel bacteria. As a test strain, we use *Cupriavidus necator* H16, a lithoautotrophic bacterium that has been engineered to produce a wide range of products from CO₂ and hydrogen. However, its low electroporation efficiency hampers the high-throughput genetic engineering required to develop *C. necator* into an industrially relevant host organism. Thus, conjugation has often been the method of choice for introducing exogenous DNA, especially when introducing large plasmids or suicide plasmids. We first propose a species-independent technique based on natively methylated DNA and Golden Gate assembly to increase one-pot cloning and electroporation efficiency by 70-fold. Second, bioinformatic tools were used to predict defense systems and develop a restriction avoidance strategy that was used to introduce suicide plasmids by electroporation to obtain a domesticated strain. The results are discussed in the context of metabolic engineering of nonmodel bacteria.

KEYWORDS: *Cupriavidus necator*, electroporation, defense systems, restriction enzymes, nonmodel bacteria, metabolic engineering

INTRODUCTION

The concentration of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere is increasing rapidly, and many different actors in the public and private sectors are rushing to develop new technologies to either store it (carbon capture and storage, CCS) or convert it into valuable products (carbon capture and utilization, CCU).¹ Nature has been operating CCU for a long time, fixing CO₂ through different metabolic pathways and transforming it into complex organic molecules,² making microorganisms a treasure trove of potential CO₂ devourers.³ In addition, with the help of synthetic biology tools, these organisms can be modified to produce useful products such as novel foods, fine chemicals, and even bulk chemicals such as 1,3 propanediol.⁴ However, most of these tools have been developed for a small selection of domesticated (heterotrophic) bacteria, such as *Escherichia coli*, and less frequently for nonmodel autotrophic microorganisms.

Cupriavidus necator H16 (formerly known as *Ralstonia eutropha* H16) is the most studied hydrogen-oxidizing bacterium, capable of using molecular hydrogen to fuel its aerobic metabolism and fix CO₂. It has been extensively engineered in the past, and many products have been obtained via metabolic engineering and heterologous enzyme expression.^{5,6} Since hydrogen can be obtained via electrolysis using green electricity, this microbe could be used in carbon-negative processes. However, there is still a bottleneck in the

widespread use of *C. necator* and the application of modern synthetic biology tools. While many plasmids, promoters and ribosome binding sites (RBSs) have been characterized,⁷ DNA delivery is mostly based on conjugation from *E. coli* S17-1,⁸ which impairs high-throughput genetic modifications, making the engineering process cumbersome and time-consuming. Several research groups have attempted to improve electroporation efficiency or chemical transformation of *C. necator* through protocol optimization,^{9–11} plasmid design,^{9,12} and strain engineering.¹³ However, many recent studies still rely on conjugation for DNA delivery. Thus, DNA delivery remains a critical bottleneck for the application of modern synthetic biology tools.¹⁴

The main cause of the low electroporation efficiency in *C. necator* is thought to be the presence of various restriction-modification systems (RM systems), which are common in nondomesticated bacteria.¹³ In their diverse ecological niches, bacteria use modification enzymes to mark their DNA by methylating nucleotides in specific patterns. This allows cells to

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Figure 1. Steps needed to increase the electroporation efficiency in the nonmodel bacterium *C. necator* H16. (A) Using Golden Gate assembly with natively methylated DNA increases electroporation efficiency in *C. necator* H16 without knowing any information on its defense arsenal; (b) Analysis and characterization of endogenous defense systems by bioinformatic prediction and experimental confirmation. These systems can then be overcome by restriction avoidance or by rational strain engineering.

Table 1. Strains and Plasmids Used in This Study

strain	genotype ^a	source or reference
<i>C. necator</i> H16/ <i>C. necator</i> wt	<i>Cupriavidus necator</i> H16 (DSM 428)	DSMZ
<i>C. necator</i> ΔRM	<i>C. necator</i> H16 ΔE6A55_RS00030 ΔE6A55_RS00035 ΔE6A55_RS00040 ΔE6A55_RS00045	this study
<i>C. necator</i> Δwad	<i>C. necator</i> H16 ΔE6A55_RS00090 ΔE6A55_RS00095 ΔE6A55_RS00100 ΔE6A55_RS00105	this study
<i>C. necator</i> ΔΔ	<i>C. necator</i> Δwad ΔE6A55_RS00030 ΔE6A55_RS00035 ΔE6A55_RS00040 ΔE6A55_RS00045	this study
<i>E. coli</i> DH5α	<i>F-Φ80lacZΔM15 Δ(lacZYA-argF) U169 recA1 endA1 hsdR17(rk-, mk+) phoA supE44 thi-1 gyrA96 relA1 λ-</i>	ThermoFisher Scientific
<i>E. coli</i> dam ⁻ /dcm ⁻	<i>ara-14 leuB6 fhuA31 lacY1 tsx78 gln V44 galK2 galT22 mcrA dcm-6 hisG4 rfbD1 R(zgb210::Tn10) TetS endA1 rspL136 (StrR) dam13::Tn9 (CamR) xylA-5 mtl-1 thi-1 mcrB1 hsdR</i>	New England Biolabs
<i>E. coli</i> S17-1	(DSM 9079) <i>RP4-2(Km::Tn7,Tc::Mu-1) pro-82 recA1 endA1 thiE1 hsdR17 creCS10</i>	Simon et al. ⁸ DSMZ
<i>P. pantotrophus</i> plasmid	<i>Paracoccus pantotrophus</i> GB 17 (DSM 2944) characteristics ^a	DSMZ source or reference
pCAT201	pBBR1 <i>ori</i> ; <i>Km^r</i> ; <i>lacZ</i>	Azubuikue et al. ¹²
pCAT_par	pCAT201; RP4 <i>parABCDE</i>	this study
pCATMt	pCAT201; insertion of 12 nt (GCAAGCAGGCATC)	this study
pMVRha	pCAT_par; <i>pJ5[C2]-spisPink</i> ; <i>rhaRS</i> ; RP4 <i>oriT</i>	this study
RSF1010-GFP	RSF1010 <i>ori</i> ; <i>Km^r</i> ; <i>J23100-B0034m-GFPmut3</i>	this study
pLO3	<i>Km^r</i> <i>sacB</i> , RP4 <i>oniT</i> , ColE1 <i>ori</i>	Lenz and Friedrich ³⁷
pLO3RM	pLO3; silent mutation in restriction enzyme recognition site; 1 kb homology regions	this study
pLO3wad	pLO3; silent mutation in restriction enzyme recognition site; 1 kb homology regions	this study

^aDetailed strain and plasmid construction are described in the Supporting Information.

distinguish between self- and nonself-DNA to avoid phages and other mobile genetic elements (MGEs).¹⁵ Several strategies have been identified to overcome the barrier posed by RM systems: (a) plasmid modification for restriction avoidance: DNA molecules were pretreated to be recognized as “self” by the host RM system, achieved through *in vitro* methylation¹⁶ or by using a shuttle strain that correctly modified the DNA;¹⁷ (b) plasmid design for restriction avoidance: by rational elimination of recognition patterns, plasmids could be rendered “invisible” to the bacterial immune system;¹⁸ (c) temporary inactivation of restriction enzymes: in some species, heat-shock pretreatment temporarily inactivated plasmid restriction;^{19,20} (d) deletion of restriction enzymes: cells

lacking restriction enzymes have been selected through random mutagenesis or rational engineering, “domesticating” the strain for easier use.²¹ All these methods require information about the organism’s genome and methylome, and recently novel algorithms for *de novo* pattern identification have been developed to aid the process.^{22,23}

While these examples focused on RM systems, recent advances in the field have led to the discovery of dozens of new defense systems capable of blocking incoming genetic elements. Most of these have only been tested against phages, but some operons can also interfere with plasmid transformation or reduce plasmid stability. Examples include the Wadjet system,²⁴ prokaryotic Argonaute proteins,²⁵ Cas

Figure 2. Restriction-Modification systems impair large plasmid electroporation. (A) Comparison of three different electroporation protocols using two benchmark plasmids, pCAT201 (red) and pCAT_par (blue). 50 μ L of competent *C. necator* H16 cells were transformed with 50 ng of plasmid. The protocols 1, 2, and 3 were derived from Ehsaan et al.,⁹ Azubuikie et al.,¹² and Tee et al.,¹¹ respectively. The protocols were modified as described in [Materials and Methods](#) and [Supporting Information](#). (B) Transformation efficiencies of the same plasmid (pCAT_par) extracted from *E. coli* DH5 α and *C. necator* H16. For each condition tested, three transformations were performed (geometric mean and standard deviation reported). Statistical analysis is described in the [Materials and Methods](#) Section.

proteins,²⁶ and other systems.²⁷ Bioinformatic tools have also been developed to identify these systems from genomic information.^{28,29}

In this study, using *C. necator* H16 as an example, we provide a roadmap (Figure 1) for increasing electroporation efficiency in nonmodel bacteria by applying different methods and tools to characterize its defense arsenal and ultimately increase electroporation efficiency. First, we developed a new method that allows one-pot cloning and electroporation of natively methylated DNA. This method is technically species-independent and could improve initial screenings in other nonmodel bacteria. Second, we investigated defense systems in *C. necator* H16 by using bioinformatic tools and databases, and used ad-hoc plasmids to investigate the role of each restriction enzyme during electroporation. Finally, we deleted three promising operons and obtained *C. necator* Δ RM, a strain with increased electroporation efficiency. Thus, we aim to contribute to the improved engineerability of *C. necator* H16 and provide a roadmap for DNA delivery in newly isolated bacteria.

RESULTS

Restriction-Modification Systems Impair Large Plasmid Electroporation. We first investigated three different electroporation protocols using the small plasmid pCAT201 (3198 bp) as a benchmark (Figure 2A, Table 1).^{9,11,12} We found the protocol derived from Tee et al. to be the most efficient and used it for all subsequent experiments. During our experiments, we also discovered that plating on LB agar supplemented with 200 mg/L kanamycin sometimes led to the growth of colonies without plasmid (escaper colonies) when plating at high cell density. The issue disappeared when we supplemented 400 mg/L kanamycin, while the colony count did not change (Supporting Information, Figure S1). From then on, we used the higher concentration for selection after electroporation. We then increased the size of the plasmid and created plasmid pCAT_par (5448 bp) by cloning the partitioning region of plasmid RP4 (*parCBA*, *parDE*) into pCAT201.³⁰ Since *C. necator* H16 is known for its plasmid instability, expression plasmids often contain this or other

stabilizing regions to ensure correct plasmid segregation.^{31–34} The partitioning region contains a toxin-antitoxin operon (*parDE*) and a system that includes a site-specific recombination system mediating resolution of plasmid multimers (*parCBA*).^{35,36}

However, while the increase in size was only modest (2250 bp), the loss of electroporation efficiency was significant (Figure 2A). For all protocols, a 100 to 1000-fold loss of electroporation efficiency compared to pCAT201 was observed. While protocol optimization may indeed affect efficiency, these experiments also highlight that the bottleneck for larger plasmids lies elsewhere and we hypothesized a major role for RM systems in this phenomenon. Thus, we compared the natively methylated pCAT_par (extracted from *C. necator*) with an incorrectly methylated one (extracted from *E. coli* DH5 α) to confirm that the RM system was the cause of the reduced efficiency (Figure 2B). Indeed, when the plasmid was extracted from the host, the loss of efficiency was completely recovered, and electroporation efficiencies comparable to pCAT201 were achieved. Similar results were briefly mentioned in a previous study.³⁸ This result suggests a strong involvement of RM systems in electroporation, as we observed that using correctly methylated plasmids drastically improves transformation efficiency. While protocol optimization can improve the electroporation of small plasmids, restriction avoidance is necessary as plasmid size increases.

Combination of Golden Gate Assembly and Natively Methylated DNA Enables High-Efficiency Transformation of Nonmodel Bacteria. The sharp difference in electroporation efficiency between *E. coli*-methylated and natively methylated DNA has been observed in many nonmodel bacteria, such as *P. putida*, *P. aeruginosa*,³⁹ *Actinomyces viscosus*, *Actinomyces naeslundii*,⁴⁰ *Caldimonas manganoxidans*,⁴¹ *Campylobacter jejuni*,⁴² *Salmonella enteritidis*,⁴³ and *Staphylococcus carnosus*.²⁰ Therefore, it can be assumed that RM systems are often the main bottleneck for DNA delivery in bacteria and that they can be avoided by transforming a natively methylated plasmid. We hypothesized that using a plasmid extracted directly from *C. necator* for subsequent cloning would significantly improve electroporation efficiency. Skipping *E. coli* amplification after DNA

Figure 3. Using Golden Gate assembly with natively methylated DNA increases electroporation efficiency. (A) Graphical explanation of the protocol. Plasmid pMVRha is either extracted from *C. necator* H16 (green star) or *E. coli* DH5 α (red star). Using a plasmid extracted from the host organism as a backbone creates a final plasmid with a hybrid methylation pattern; (B) Efficiency of one-pot Golden Gate assembly and electroporation using as backbone pMVRha extracted from *E. coli* DH5 α and *C. necator* H16, respectively. For each condition tested, three Golden Gate reactions and transformations were performed (geometric mean and standard deviation reported). Statistical analysis is described in the [Materials and Methods](#) Section; (C) Map of the plasmid pMVRha; (D) Specific fluorescence of *C. necator* pMVRha-GFP after induction with different concentrations of rhamnose. Five random colonies were picked and tested (mean and standard deviation reported).

assembly preserves the host methylation pattern and avoids restriction enzymes. The backbone (extracted from the native host) would be correctly methylated, while the insert would be either unmethylated (PCR-amplified) or methylated in the wrong pattern (*E. coli*) (Figure 3A). In this case, the restriction enzymes would only recognize and target the short insert. We decided to further investigate this hypothesis by using Golden Gate assembly, which does not rely on PCR amplification of the backbone (in this case removing the methylation patterns) and can ligate multiple inserts with high efficiency⁴⁴ (Figure 3A).

First, we created the plasmid pMVRha (8437 bp) (Figure 3C), a Golden Gate-compatible plasmid based on the pCAT201 backbone (Table 1). It contains the *par* stabilizing region,³⁰ the origin of transfer from RP4 (*oriT*),⁸ a rhamnose-inducible promoter (*RhaRS* + *P_{Rha}*),⁴⁵ *BsaI* restriction sites, and a chromoprotein gene as cloning marker (*spisPink*).⁴⁶ Colonies containing unrestricted pMVRha show pink color on plate. Notably, the *BsaI* overhangs are compatible with all MoClo libraries for easy cloning of genes already available in a donor plasmid.⁴⁷

We then assessed whether this backbone could be used for one-pot Golden Gate assembly and electroporation. We transformed *C. necator* H16 with pMVRha via electroporation, extracted it, and obtained natively methylated DNA. The same plasmid was also extracted from *E. coli* DH5 α . We then used these two plasmids as backbones for Golden Gate assembly

and cloned the gene *gfpmut3* from a donor plasmid using *BsaI*.⁴⁷ The donor plasmid containing the gene was extracted from *E. coli* DH5 α , and 2 μ L of each assembly mix were used directly for *C. necator* electroporation. Using the plasmid extracted from *C. necator* as the backbone increased the efficiency 70-fold (Figure 3B), and more than 12,000 colonies could be obtained after a single electroporation. All colonies were white, confirming successful *spisPink* excision. Thus, using a natively methylated backbone increases efficiency, even if the insert is incorrectly methylated. To confirm that all colonies contained the correct insert, 90 randomly selected colonies showed GFP production after rhamnose induction (Figure S4). Five colonies were randomly selected to confirm the induction parameters, and GFP expression was measured after induction with different concentrations of rhamnose (Figure 3D). To confirm that this strategy is also effective in other nonmodel bacteria, we followed the same procedure with *Paracoccus pantotrophus* GB 17 (DSM 2944), a facultative lithoautotrophic bacterium previously studied for wastewater denitrification and polyhydroxyalkanoate production.⁴⁸ Previously, this bacterium could not be transformed by electroporation with a pBBR1-based plasmid,⁴⁹ and we speculated that this was due to plasmid restriction. Plasmid pMVRha was successfully transformed by conjugation, and the resulting strain showed *spisPink* production, proving that the cloning marker could be used in other organisms (Figure S5A). The plasmid was then extracted and used for Golden Gate assembly

Table 2. Selected Defense Systems Identified in *C. necator* H16^a

defense system	identified by	genes	putative recognition pattern
restriction enzyme (type I)	PD, RE, DF	E6A55_RS00030	GAYNNNNNCTTGY
restriction enzymes (type IV)	RE	E6A55_RS00040; E6A55_RS00045	
orphan methyltransferase	RE	E6A55_RS13360	GTWWAC
Wadjet system (type III)	PD, DF	E6A55_RS00090 (JetD3); E6A55_RS00095 (JetC3); E6A55_RS00100 (JetB3); E6A55_RS00105 (JetA3)	

^aIn "Identified by": DF: DefenseFinder, RE: REBASE, PD:PADLOC. The putative methylated residues are bold. The complete list can be found in the Supporting Information (Table S1).

Figure 4. Predicted type I and type IV RM systems are present and decrease electroporation efficiency. (A) Transformation efficiency of plasmids pCAT201 and pCATMt in *C. necator* H16; (B) Transformation efficiency of two benchmark plasmids (red: pCAT_par; blue: pMVRha) extracted from *E. coli* DH5a, *E. coli dam⁻/dcm⁻*, and *C. necator* H16. For each condition tested, three transformations were performed (geometric mean and standard deviation reported). Statistical analysis is described in the Materials and Methods Section.

and direct electroporation of the cloning mixture. Using the natively methylated backbone increased efficiency 47-fold, and GFPmut3 production was visible (Figure S5B–C). However, the promoter was also active in the absence of rhamnose.

This simple and rapid technique could dramatically improve engineering efforts in nonmodel bacteria. All organisms compatible with the pBBR1 origin of replication could be transformed with pMVRha by electroporation or conjugation. After this initial transformation, the natively methylated plasmid can be used as a backbone for Golden Gate assembly, ensuring higher electroporation efficiency.

Bioinformatic Tools Identify RM Systems, Restriction Sites, and Other Potential Transformation Bottlenecks. After successfully confirming that RM systems impair plasmid electroporation in *C. necator* H16, we aimed to identify the restriction enzymes and their corresponding recognition sequences to develop an appropriate restriction avoidance strategy (e.g., plasmid design, use of premethylated plasmid, or temporary restriction inactivation). Knowledge of the genome sequence and the methylome is required to identify the responsible RM systems. Interestingly, both data sets for *C. necator* H16 were already available online at NCBI^{50,51} and REBASE, respectively (Little et al, 2019, REBASE ref No. 28544).

We analyzed the genome of *C. necator* H16 using three online defense system identification tools, REBASE, DefenseFinder and PADLOC.^{28,29} REBASE contains information regarding bacterial methylation and RM systems,⁵⁰ while DefenseFinder and PADLOC are both able to predict a vast array of defense systems, including RM enzymes. While some defense systems were identified by only one of the tools, there

was significant overlap, allowing us to predict several operons and their potential role in defense (Table S1). We focused our analysis on four of the systems identified (Table 2).

Two methylation patterns were annotated in REBASE, the pattern GAYNNNNNCTTGY is predicted to be methylated (m6A) by a putative type I RM system, which was identified by all algorithms. The pattern GTWWAC is predicted to be methylated by an orphan methylase without an associated restriction enzyme. This lack of restriction element could be caused by incorrect prediction, incomplete horizontal transfer, mutation, or involvement of the methyltransferase in processes unrelated to defense. Two other potential RM enzymes were identified, a type IV restriction enzyme (capable of degrading incorrectly methylated DNA⁵²) and another putative orphan methylase (Table S1).

Many other defense systems were identified in the genome, such as AVAST, Zorya, and Gabija (Table S1).^{24,53} However, our attention was focused on the putative Wadjet system, one of the few defense systems that has been shown to act against plasmids by reducing electroporation efficiency and/or decreasing plasmid stability. When reconstituted *in vitro*, Wadjet systems were able to selectively cut plasmid DNA.^{24,54–56} Since *C. necator* H16 is known for its plasmid instability, we hypothesized a role of the putative Wadjet system in plasmid loss.

Ad-hoc Test Plasmids to Analyze the Role of Each RM System. To experimentally confirm the bioinformatic predictions of the three tools and clarify the role of these genes in electroporation efficiency, several test plasmids were designed for transformation of *C. necator* H16. First, we created a plasmid to confirm the presence of the type I RM

Figure 5. Deletion of the type I and IV RM systems partially restored electroporation efficiency. Transformation efficiency of plasmids pCAT201, pCATMt, pCAT_par and pMVRha in *C. necator* H16, Δ RM, Δ wad, $\Delta\Delta$; (A) Plasmids were extracted from *E. coli* DH5a; (B) Plasmids were extracted from *E. coli* dam^-/dcm^- . Three different batches of competent cells were transformed (geometric mean and standard deviation reported). Statistical analysis is described in the [Materials and Methods](#) Section.

system. We slightly modified pCAT201 by introducing a single restriction pattern (GAYNNNNNCTTGY, 12 bp) and obtained the plasmid pCATMt. When we compared the electroporation efficiency, we observed a drastic loss (5225-fold) with plasmid pCATMt compared to pCAT201 (Figure 4A), although the two plasmids differ by only 12 bp. Therefore, not only is a type I restriction enzyme present, but the pattern predicted in REBASE was also correct.

Interestingly, deletion of the same gene (*H16_A0006*) was the most successful deletion in previous efforts to create a domesticated *C. necator* strain.¹³ The transformation efficiency of their test plasmid pBBR1-rfp increased 1658-fold in the deleted strain. However, another group recreated the same strain and obtained more limited results (3-fold increase).⁹ We found that the test plasmid pBBR1-rfp contained the restriction pattern identified by our bioinformatic analysis. This confirms the validity of their observation and explains the results obtained later. A similar phenomenon occurred in another study where a kanamycin resistance protein was deemed “unsuitable” for *C. necator* due to the lack of colonies obtained. We speculate that the cause is the gene instead, which contains the identified restriction pattern.¹² The recognition pattern is long and should be rare in plasmids. Notably, many of the plasmids used in *C. necator* H16 contain this pattern (e.g., pKRC, pKRha, pBBR1MCS2),^{45,57,58} which highlights the importance of using different test plasmids to avoid artifacts.

To verify the presence of the type IV restriction system, we used the previously assembled plasmid pCAT_par. This plasmid was chosen for several reasons. First, pCAT_par does not contain the previously identified restriction pattern. Therefore, the contribution of the type I RM system is expected to be neglectable. Second, pCAT_par showed different transformation efficiencies when extracted from *E. coli* and *C. necator*, indicating that another restriction enzyme should be involved. Finally, this plasmid contains a GTWWAC pattern that is methylated in *C. necator*. This pattern was predicted to be methylated by an orphan methylase and may be involved in defense or other mechanisms.

To isolate the role of the type IV restriction enzyme, we transformed pCAT_par in the shuttle strain *E. coli* dam^-/dcm^- to obtain unmethylated DNA.⁵⁹ We then compared the transformation efficiency of plasmid DNA extracted from *E.*

coli DH5a (methylated in the patterns GATC and CCWGG), *E. coli* dam^-/dcm^- (not methylated), and *C. necator* (methylated in the patterns GAYNNNNNCTTGY and GTWWAC) (Figure 4B). Interestingly, using unmethylated DNA completely restored transformation efficiency, which was also confirmed with the longer plasmid pMVRha (Figure 4B). Therefore, we assume that only the type I RM system and the type IV system are involved in the loss of electroporation efficiency, and the orphan methylase is involved in defense-unrelated mechanisms. Notably, there is still a decrease in efficiency from pCAT_par to pMVRha even when unmethylated or natively methylated DNA is used.

Deletion of Defense Systems by Electroporation of Suicide Plasmids. After confirming the presence of two active RM systems in *C. necator* H16, we created a domesticated strain by gene deletion using the suicide plasmid pLO3, previously used in *C. necator* genome engineering.³⁷ Suicide plasmids have a lower transformation efficiency than normal plasmids due to the low frequency of genomic integration. We used the previously collected information to transform this plasmid by electroporation. To do so, we used a combination of plasmid engineering and premethylation. First, we identified a restriction sequence (GAYNNNNNCTTGY) in the suicide plasmid and used targeted mutagenesis to remove it by introducing a silent mutation. Second, we transformed the shuttle strain *E. coli* dam^-/dcm^- with this plasmid to remove DNA methylation. We then successfully transformed *C. necator* by electroporation, although with the expected low efficiency (~ 8 CFU/ μ g DNA). After *sacB*-mediated counter selection and confirmation, we obtained the strain *C. necator* Δ RM (Table 1), where both the putative type I and type IV restriction enzymes were deleted. We used the same technique to delete the Wadjet operon (*C. necator* Δ wad) and to create a double-deleted strain called *C. necator* $\Delta\Delta$ (Table 1). Deletions were confirmed via genomic DNA extraction, PCR amplification of the genomic region and sequencing of the amplicons (Figures S2, S3).

We then characterized these new strains using plasmids pCAT201, pCATMt, pCAT_par, and pMVRha. We performed transformations with plasmids extracted from *E. coli* DH5a and *E. coli* dam^-/dcm^- to quantify the role of the two RM systems in each strain (Figure 5). The transformation efficiency of plasmid pCATMt was entirely restored in the *C. necator* Δ RM

and $\Delta\Delta$ knockout strains. This proved that we had successfully deleted the type I restriction enzyme. Knocking out the predicted type IV restriction enzyme slightly increased the efficiency of the mis-methylated pCAT_par and pMVRha (Figure 5A) but did not completely restore it. In fact, plasmids extracted from *E. coli dam⁻/dcm⁻* achieved higher transformation efficiencies (Figure 5B).

Thus, another genetic element present in *C. necator* H16 must be additionally responsible for the selective decrease in transformation efficiency of incorrectly methylated plasmids. The culprit was not the Wadjet system, as deletion did not cause any change in electroporation efficiency compared to the wt strain (Figure 5A), and the double knockout strain *C. necator* $\Delta\Delta$ performed similarly to the single knockout *C. necator* Δ RM strain. However, it was reported that this defense system could decrease plasmid stability without affecting electroporation efficiency.⁵⁶

An unstable test plasmid was assembled to investigate the role of the predicted Wadjet system in plasmid instability. This plasmid contained the RSF1010 replicon, which is unstable in *C. necator* when the *par* region is not added.⁹ In addition, this plasmid contained an operon that expressed the fluorescent protein GFPmut3 using the J23100 promoter and RBS B0034m.⁶⁰ This plasmid was introduced in *C. necator* wt and *C. necator* Δ wad by electroporation, and its stability was measured. Under the conditions tested, plasmid RSF1010-GFP was lost completely after about 46 generations (Figure 6) in

Figure 6. Deletion of the putative Wadjet system did not increase plasmid stability. Plasmid stability of plasmid RSF1010-GFP in *C. necator* wt and *C. necator* Δ wad. Two cultures were analyzed for each genotype (mean and standard deviation reported).

both strains and no difference was observed between the two genotypes. Therefore, the deleted operon did not affect electroporation efficiency or plasmid stability under the chosen conditions.

DISCUSSION

Industrial biotechnology has recently shifted its attention from model organisms to a broad range of alternative bacteria, to exploit their unique metabolic capabilities. However, the domestication process is cumbersome and strain-specific. In this study, we characterized the defense systems of the lithoautotrophic bacterium *C. necator* H16 and propose a roadmap to increase electroporation efficiency in other nonmodel bacteria. *C. necator* has recently been in the spotlight due to its autotrophic metabolism and ability to

grow on formate, but its low transformation efficiency hinders extensive genetic modifications. In particular, several research groups have been working toward an increase in electroporation efficiency with promising results. Electroporation protocols have been optimized,^{9,11} small plasmids have been designed,^{9,12} and putative restriction enzymes have been deleted.¹³ These latter deletions increased electroporation efficiency, but the maximum efficiency achieved was still low (about 10^4 CFU/ μ g DNA), and thus conjugation is often the method of choice for introducing exogenous DNA.

Therefore, we used *C. necator* as a test case and first compared different electroporation protocols using small and medium size plasmids as standardized test plasmids. We obtained the highest electroporation efficiency ever reported in *C. necator* H16 (10^8 CFU/ μ g DNA), but confirmed that restriction avoidance was necessary to introduce larger plasmids. We then proposed a species-independent technique to rapidly clone and express multiple enzymes in novel strains by restriction avoidance. Indeed, using Golden Gate assembly with a natively methylated backbone (here referred to as pMVRha) allows rapid and highly efficient cloning and electroporation of multiple inserts in nonmodel bacteria (70-fold increase in electroporation efficiency in *C. necator*). This technique can be used to express multiple enzymes in newly discovered species to identify the most promising ones. For example, a library of homologues could be screened to identify the best-performing enzyme prior to genomic integration. Large libraries of enzyme variants generated by error-prone PCR could also be rapidly introduced into organisms that are recalcitrant to electroporation. The plasmid pMVRha can be used in all organisms compatible with the broad-host replicon pBBR1. In this article, pMVRha was successfully employed for direct assembly and electroporation in the facultative autotroph *Paracoccus pantotrophus*. *Pseudomonas putida* and *Vibrio natriegens* are two other pBBR1-compatible industrial chassis, both widely used due to their superior metabolic capabilities or growth rate compared to *E. coli*.^{61,62} In addition, this technique can be used for other purposes where high transformation efficiency is required. Some Cas9 plasmids, such as the CRISPRi system recently developed for *C. necator* H16, are designed for gRNA cloning using BsaI,⁶³ and a large number of gRNAs could be cloned and tested simultaneously after purification of the natively methylated backbone. However, there are some limitations. For instance, if the host organism is highly recombinogenic, pMVRha could be mutated before plasmid extraction. In addition, Golden Gate uses BsaI as the restriction enzyme, and if the host organism methylates its recognition pattern, the assembly would not be possible. In this second case, another type IIS restriction enzyme could be used instead.

After this initial screening step, whole genome sequencing using a methylation-sensitive method such as Single Molecule, Real-Time (SMRT) sequencing or Nanopore Sequencing is recommended, and bioinformatic analysis may reveal putative restriction systems, their target patterns and other defense systems.^{22,23,64} In *C. necator*, we identified two complete restriction-modification systems with their specificities and a putative Wadjet system that could influence transformation efficiency and plasmid stability in other organisms.^{24,54–56} Accordingly, ad-hoc plasmids were created to investigate the role of each predicted system. The plasmids pCATMt, pCAT_par and pMVRha were used to confirm a strong activity of the type I RM system (over 5000-fold decrease of

transformation efficiency when its restriction pattern was present), as well as the activity of a type IV restriction system against plasmids larger than pCAT201, with the effect depending on plasmid size (1927-fold decrease for pCAT_{par}, 5644-fold decrease for pMVRha). We confirmed our bioinformatic predictions and developed a restriction avoidance strategy based on plasmid design (removal of type I RM recognition patterns) and *in vivo* demethylation (using the shuttle strain *E. coli dam⁻/dcm⁻*). This greatly increased electroporation efficiency and allowed us to introduce suicide plasmids by electroporation.

Moreover, we successfully deleted both type I and type IV putative restriction enzymes, and characterized the new strains. These deletions were already described in a previous study.¹³ However, our in-depth approach led us to characterize the role of each enzyme, and we clarified a discrepancy in the results observed in a subsequent study due to the choice of the test plasmid.⁹ Surprisingly, we also discovered that a yet undiscovered defense system is still able to target methylated DNA. Furthermore, a putative Wadjet system was identified, but its deletion did not affect either transformation efficiency or plasmid stability under the tested conditions. Many other promising defense systems were identified in *C. necator* H16. A small number of targets were selected for further analysis based on the available literature information. Deletion of other predicted defense operons might elucidate which system is still active against methylated DNA. If further deletions prove unsuccessful, other methods based on random mutagenesis may be employed. Unfortunately, the role of defense systems in plasmid transformation is yet minimally explored, and thus we speculate that a broader attention to their action against plasmids could benefit the field of industrial biotechnology while shedding light on their sensing and action mechanisms.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Chemicals, Bacterial Strains, and Culture Conditions.

All chemicals used were purchased from Sigma–Aldrich Ltd., VWR International LLC, or Carl Roth GmbH in the highest purity. *C. necator* H16 (DSM 428), *P. pantotrophus* GB17 (DSM 2944) and *E. coli* S17-1 (DSM 9079) were purchased from DSMZ (Braunschweig, Germany). *E. coli* DH5 α was purchased from ThermoFisher Scientific and used as a host for cloning and plasmid propagation. *E. coli dam⁻/dcm⁻* was purchased from New England BioLabs (NEB) and used for demethylation of plasmid DNA. All microbial strains used are listed in Table 1. *C. necator*, *P. pantotrophus* and *E. coli* were generally grown in *lysogeny* broth (LB, 10 g/L tryptone, 10 g/L NaCl, 5 g/L yeast extract) or tryptic soy broth (TSB) at 30 °C (*C. necator*, *P. pantotrophus*) and 37 °C (*E. coli*). Agar agar was added to a final concentration of 2% to obtain LB agar and TSB agar. When necessary, media was supplemented with antibiotics. Media used for *C. necator* cultivation was supplemented with 20 mg L⁻¹ gentamicin, 200 or 400 mg L⁻¹ kanamycin, or 15 mg L⁻¹ tetracycline. LB supplemented with 400 mg L⁻¹ kanamycin was used for selection after electroporation. In all other situations, LB was supplemented with 200 mg L⁻¹ kanamycin. Media used for *P. pantotrophus* was supplemented with 20 mg L⁻¹ gentamicin, and 50 or 100 mg L⁻¹ kanamycin. LB supplemented with 100 mg L⁻¹ kanamycin was used for selection after electroporation. In all other situations, LB was supplemented with 50 mg L⁻¹ kanamycin. Media for *E. coli* DH5 α and *E. coli dam⁻/dcm⁻*

was supplemented with 50 mg L⁻¹ kanamycin or 15 mg L⁻¹ tetracycline.

Cloning and *E. coli* Transformation. Plasmid DNA was purified using QIAprep Spin Miniprep Kit (Qiagen) or Monarch Plasmid Miniprep Kit (NEB). When purifying plasmid DNA from *C. necator*, using less cell culture volume than recommended is advised to avoid genomic DNA contamination (e.g., 1.5–2 mL instead of 5 mL). DNA purification from PCR reaction mixtures was performed using QIAquick PCR Purification Kit (Qiagen Ltd., UK). Microbial genomic DNA was extracted using GenElute Bacterial Genomic DNA Kit (Sigma). DNA was amplified by PCR in 25 μ L reactions using Q5 High-Fidelity DNA Polymerase (NEB). All PCR reactions were set up according to the manufacturer's instructions. BsaI-HFv2, BbsI-HF, and T4 DNA ligase were purchased from New England BioLabs (NEB). DpnI and T4 Polynucleotide Kinase were purchased from ThermoFisher Scientific.

For *E. coli* transformations, 50 μ L of chemically competent cells⁶⁵ were mixed with plasmid DNA, incubated in ice for 30 min, followed by a heat shock at 42 °C for 45 s and a subsequent incubation in ice for 2 min. Cells were recovered in 950 μ L of Super Optimal broth with Catabolite repression (SOC) medium at 37 °C for 1 h, plated on LB agar with the appropriate antibiotic and incubated overnight at 37 °C.

***C. necator* Electroporation.** Electroporation of *C. necator* was performed according to protocols 1, 2, and 3 derived from Ehsaan et al.,⁹ Azubuike et al.¹² and Tee et al.,¹¹ respectively. All protocols are described in detail in the Supporting Information. Protocol 3 was generally used for the preparation of electrocompetent *C. necator* cells and electroporation, unless otherwise stated, with slight modifications to the protocol derived from Tee et al.¹¹ Briefly, *C. necator* H16 was first streaked onto a TSB agar plate and grown for 40 h. A single colony was then cultivated in SOB supplemented with 20 mg L⁻¹ gentamicin for 16 h at 30 °C. Fresh SOB supplemented with gentamicin was inoculated with the preculture at an initial OD₆₀₀ of 0.1 and cultivated at 30 °C. When the cells reached an OD₆₀₀ of 0.4–0.6, they were transferred onto ice and chilled for 5–10 min. The cells were then transferred to 50 mL falcon tubes and centrifuged at 6000g at 4 °C for 2 min. The supernatant was removed, and cells were resuspended in 25 mL of 50 mM CaCl₂ by briefly using a vortex. They were then incubated for 15 min on ice. The cells were then centrifuged at 6500g at 4 °C for 2 min, and the supernatant was removed. Cells were washed twice using 25 and 15 mL of ice-cold 0.2 M sucrose, respectively. At the end of each wash, cells were centrifuged at 6500g at 4 °C for 2–3 min, and the supernatant was decanted. The cell pellet was finally resuspended in 1/100 of the initial volume (e.g., 100 mL initial cell culture to 1 mL final resuspension volume). 50 μ L aliquots of competent cells were transferred into 1.5 mL centrifuge tubes, snap-frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored at –80 °C until further use. For electroporation, each aliquot was thawed on ice for 20 min, transferred into a chilled 1 mm electroporation cuvette, mixed with 50–200 ng of plasmid DNA, incubated for 2–5 min and electroporated (25 μ F, 200 Ω , 1.15 kV). 950 μ L of SOB supplemented with fructose (20 mM) were immediately added and the cells were transferred to a 2 mL centrifuge tube for outgrowth at 30 °C for 2 h. After the outgrowth, cells were diluted and plated on selective media.

When comparing different conditions, a log₁₀ transformation was applied to the transformation efficiency values

[CFU/ μg_{DNA}] to obtain homogeneity of variances between samples. Two-sample *t* test was used when comparing two samples. When comparing multiple conditions, one-way ANOVA and Tukey's multiple comparison test were used. Due to the log10 transformation, the statistical tests compare the original data's geometric means. Therefore, geometric means and SD were reported in the graphs. * = adjusted *p*-value <0.05; ** = adjusted *p*-value <0.01; *** = adjusted *p*-value <0.001; **** = adjusted *p*-value <0.0001.

Plasmid Construction. Oligonucleotide primers were synthesized by Eurofins Genomics (Ebersberg, Germany; Supporting Information, Table S1). Plasmids were sequenced by Sanger sequencing (Macrogen Europe). pCAT201¹² was purchased from Addgene (#134878) and used as a backbone for further plasmid construction. Plasmid pLO3³⁷ was kindly provided by Dr. Oliver Lenz (TU Berlin, Germany). Other genetic parts were PCR-amplified or synthesized from Twist Bioscience. After PCR amplification, template DNA was removed by adding 0.5 μL of DpnI to the PCR mix and incubating the mixture at 37 °C for 1 h. Detailed plasmid construction is described in the Supporting Information. Plasmids pCAT_par, pMVRha, RSF1010-GFP and pMVRha-GFP were constructed using Golden Gate Assembly.⁴⁴ Briefly, for pCAT_par and pMVRha, 75 ng of PCR-amplified backbone were mixed with fragments in a 1:2 molar ratio. For pMVRha-GFP assembly, 75 ng of acceptor plasmid pMVRha were mixed with 75 ng of donor vector c11.⁴⁷ For RSF1010-GFP, 75 ng of PCR-amplified backbone was mixed with 75 ng of each donor vector (p13, r03, c11, and te06). Golden Gate reactions were carried out in a total volume of 10 μL by mixing the DNA, Milli-Q water, T4 DNA ligase buffer, T4 DNA ligase (200 U), and BsaI-HFv2 or BbsI-HF (6 U). The mixture was then incubated in a thermocycler using the following program: (37 °C, 5 min \rightarrow 16 °C, 5 min) \times 15 \rightarrow 60 °C, 5 min. Plasmids pLOWad and pLORM were constructed using Gibson assembly.⁶⁶ Sequences of pCATMt, pCAT_par and pMVRha are reported in the Supporting Information.

Fluorescence Measurement. To determine the dose-response of GFP expression from plasmid pMVRha-GFP after rhamnose induction, OD₆₀₀ and GFPmut3 fluorescence were measured over time using a Biolector (M2P Laboratories, Baesweiler, Germany) in 96-well plates (Greiner Bio-One) with a filling volume of 200 μL . Precultures were cultivated overnight at 30 °C at 200 rpm in glass tubes containing 2 mL of LB supplemented with 200 mg L⁻¹ kanamycin. Cultures were then inoculated to an OD₆₀₀ of 0.2 in LB containing varying amounts of L-rhamnose. The Biolector was set to 30 °C, 900 rpm and humidity control of 85%. Two internal filter modules of the device were used for online measurement. Fluorescence of GFPmut3 was measured at an excitation wavelength of 488 nm and an emission wavelength of 520 nm with a gain 60. Biomass was determined at 620 nm with a gain 40 as scattered light. Scattered light was correlated to OD₆₀₀ with a dilution series of a stationary phase culture. After collecting the data, each value was blanked using a well with empty LB media. To determine specific fluorescence, fluorescence intensity was divided by scattered light. To test whether all the colonies were assembled correctly after Golden Gate assembly, several colonies from each electroporation plate were inoculated in a 96-deep well plate (EnzyScreen) filled with 500 μL LB and kanamycin (200 mg L⁻¹) supplemented with 5 mM rhamnose. The plate was then incubated overnight at 30 °C, 300 rpm. 100 μL were then transferred to a 96-well

plate (Greiner), and blue light was used to qualitatively observe GFPmut3 fluorescence.

Gene Deletion. Knockout plasmids pLOWad and pLORM were first transferred in *E. coli dam⁻/dcm⁻* to remove DNA methylation. The purified plasmids were then used for *C. necator* H16 electroporation. Transconjugants were selected on LB supplemented with 15 mg L⁻¹ tetracycline. 1–4 positive colonies were picked and grown overnight in 5 mL of low salt LB (LSLB) without any supplementation (10 g L⁻¹ tryptone, 5 g L⁻¹ NaCl, 5 g L⁻¹ yeast extract). Dilutions were made, and 100 μL of each dilution were plated on LSLB-agar supplemented with 150 g L⁻¹ sucrose and incubated at 30 °C for 48 h to select for *sacB* negative colonies (i.e., double recombination). Colony PCR was performed on sucrose-resistant colonies using a flanking pair of oligonucleotide primers to screen for the double crossover deletion mutants. Promising clones were then grown overnight for genomic DNA extraction. Flanking primers were used to amplify the targeted region, and the amplicon was sequenced to confirm deletion (Supporting Information, Figures S2 and S3).

Plasmid Stability. Single colonies were inoculated in 2 mL of LB supplemented with 200 mg L⁻¹ kanamycin and grown overnight at 30 °C, 200 rpm. The cultures were then diluted 1:100 in fresh LB without antibiotics and grown for 24 h. The dilution was then repeated each day. Every day, OD₆₀₀ of each culture was measured, and the cultures were serially diluted and plated in LB agar without supplementation. After 3 days, colonies were counted. GFP-positive colonies were identified using blue light. The ratio of GFP-positive colonies and total colonies was used to determine plasmid presence. Generation number *n* was calculated using the following formula:

$$n = \log_2 \frac{\text{OD}_{600}(\text{final})}{\text{OD}_{600}(\text{initial})}$$

■ ASSOCIATED CONTENT

SI Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge at <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acssynbio.4c00380>.

Detailed protocols for plasmid construction, conjugation, and preparation of electrocompetent cells (Experimental Section). List of putative defense systems identified in *C. necator* H16 (Table S1). Primers used in the study (Table S2). Transformation efficiency in LB agar supplemented with 200 mg/L and 400 mg/L kanamycin (Figure S1). Schematic representation of genomic deletions in strains *C. necator* ΔRM and *C. necator* Δwad (Figures S2–S3). GFP expression of randomly picked colonies after pMVRha-GFP cloning (Figure S4). Nucleotide sequences of plasmids pCATMt, pCAT_par, and pMVRha (Plasmid sequences section). *P. pantotrophus* strains containing pMVRha (Figure S5A), electroporation efficiency of pMVRha-GFP cloning mix (Figure S5C) and GFP expression of randomly picked *P. pantotrophus* pMVRha-GFP colonies (Figure S5B) (PDF)

■ AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding Author

Sandy Schmidt – Department of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Biology, Groningen Research Institute of Pharmacy, University of Groningen, Groningen 9713AV, The

Netherlands; orcid.org/0000-0002-8443-8805;
Email: s.schmidt@rug.nl

Authors

Matteo Vajente – Department of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Biology, Groningen Research Institute of Pharmacy, University of Groningen, Groningen 9713AV, The Netherlands; orcid.org/0000-0002-8589-9072

Riccardo Clerici – Institute of Applied Microbiology (iAMB), Aachen Biology and Biotechnology (ABBT), RWTH Aachen University, 52074 Aachen, Germany; orcid.org/0009-0009-9721-1544

Hendrik Ballerstedt – Institute of Applied Microbiology (iAMB), Aachen Biology and Biotechnology (ABBT), RWTH Aachen University, 52074 Aachen, Germany

Lars M. Blank – Institute of Applied Microbiology (iAMB), Aachen Biology and Biotechnology (ABBT), RWTH Aachen University, 52074 Aachen, Germany; orcid.org/0000-0003-0961-4976

Complete contact information is available at:
<https://pubs.acs.org/10.1021/acssynbio.4c00380>

Author Contributions

M.V. and S.S. designed the research. M.V. and R.C. carried out the experiments. M.V. analyzed the data and wrote the paper. M.V., H.B., L.M.B., and S.S. read and revised the manuscript. H.B., L.M.B., and S.S. supervised the research. All authors have read and approved the final manuscript.

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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